

РОЛЬ АРТЕРІАЛЬНОЇ ГІПЕРТЕНЗІЇ У РОЗВИТКУ ТА ПЕРЕБІГУ ФІБРИЛЯЦІЇ ПЕРЕДСЕРДЬ ПІСЛЯ ПЕРЕНЕСЕНОЇ КОРОНАВІРУСНОЇ ІНФЕКЦІЇ

THE ROLE OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND THE COURSE OF ATRIAL FIBRILLATION AFTER CORONAVIRUS INFECTION

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Introduction: It is known, that arterial hypertension (AH) is the main cause of atrial fibrillation (AF).

The aim of our study was to assess the parameters of systemic hemodynamics as a predictor of AF development after coronavirus infection (CI) and to assess the course of AF after infection with COVID-19 (CI) depending on the presence of hypertension.

Material and methods: We examined 118 patients with AF, at the age of 62.5 ± 0.09 years with AF, who, on average, 6.2 ± 0.5 months had undergone CI. Of these, 14 people (8.4%) also had atrial flutter. 72 people (61 %) had AF before CI (1st group of patients). From 72 patients with AF, aged 64.5 ± 1.2 years, who, on average, 6.2 ± 0.5 months underwent CI, 59 (81.9%) people had AH (subgroup '1A' patients). The remaining 13 (18.1%) patients did not have hypertension (subgroup '1B' patients). The remaining 46 patients (39 %) had no history of this arrhythmia (2nd group of patients). Office blood pressure was measured according to the generally accepted method.

Results: In the 1st group, the indicators of systolic blood pressure (SBP) were significantly lower than in the 2nd group (131.4 ± 1.72 and 139.5 ± 2.99 mm Hg, $p < 0.05$), indicators of diastolic blood pressure (DBP) (81.5 ± 0.74 and 87.9 ± 2.41 Hg, $p < 0.05$), and heart rate (HR) (83.0 ± 1.86 and 98.0 ± 2.4 bpm, $p < 0.05$). This difference in the groups was more significant between patients with hypertension: SBP, respectively (134.7 ± 1.5 and 143.9 ± 3.8 mm Hg, $p < 0.05$), DBP (83.3 ± 1.1 and 90.5 ± 2.6 Hg, $p < 0.05$), and heart rate HR (83.0 ± 1.86 and 98.0 ± 2.4 bpm, $p < 0.001$). In addition, in group 1, AH was found significantly less frequently (in 59

out of 72 patients, 81.9%) than in patients in group 2 (in 42 out of 46 patients, 91.3%), $p < 0.05$.

When analyzing the course of AF after CI in these groups, it was found that an increase in the frequency of AF paroxysms was observed in a significantly larger number of patients in subgroup '1A' (32 out of 59 people, 54.2%) than in patients in subgroup '1B' (in 3 out of 13 people, 23.1%), $p < 0.001$, the duration of AF paroxysms also increased more significantly in a larger number of patients in subgroup '1A' (in 29 out of 59 people, 49.2%), than in patients of subgroup '1B' (in 4 of 13 people, 30.8%), $p < 0.001$, and the surrogate indicator of deterioration in the course of AF (an increase in the frequency or duration of AF paroxysms) was also higher in subgroup '1A' (in 36 of 59 patients, 61.0%), compared with subgroup '1B' (5 out of 13 patients), $p < 0.001$.

Conclusion: An increase in SBP, DBP HR and AH, are predictors of the development of AF in patients after CI. The presence of AH significantly worsens the course of AF after CI, increasing the frequency of paroxysms of this arrhythmia and their duration.